

Article title: The smallest *Zosterophyllum* plant from the Lower Devonian of South China and the divergent life history strategies in zosterophylloids

Authors: Pu Huang, Jia-Shu Wang, Yi-Ling Wang, Lu Liu, Jing-Yu Zhao, and Jin-Zhuang Xue

Journal name: *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*

Article DOI: 10.1098/rspb.2024.2337

Electronic supplementary material

Figures S1 to S5

Tables S1 to S4

Figure S1. The traffic map of fossil locality (a) and lithological column of the Mangshan Group at the Baoyang section with plant-bearing beds (b), modified from ref. [1]. Abbreviations: MS, mudstone; SS, siltstone; ST, sandstone.

Figure S2. Sketch illustrations showing morphological descriptors of *Zosterophyllum* species and other related plants. (a, b) After ref. [2] for *Zosterophyllum myretonianum*. (c–e) Abaxial view, lateral view, and adaxial view of a sporangium, respectively. In our measurements and estimation of TSA of individual plants, the number of sporangia in a spike or a fertile region refers to only the number of visible sporangia rather than all estimated sporangia; the axial width indicates either the width of vegetative axes or that of fertile ones; and the sporangial height includes only the length of sporangial body (that is, excluding sporangial stalk).

Figure S3. *Zosterophyllum baoyangense* sp. nov. (*a, b*) PB203563, part and counterpart of a fertile axis; (*c*) Enlarged view of the basal portion of the spike in *a*. Arrows point to the distal valve of a sporangium in lateral view (lower arrow) and sporangium with peripheral rim (upper arrow); (*d*) Details of the distal portion of spike in *b*, showing sporangium with peripheral rim (arrow). Scale bars: (*a, b*), 5 mm; (*c–d*), 1 mm.

Figure S4. Line drawings of the spikes of *Zosterophyllum baoyangense* sp. nov., based on specimens PB203562 (a) and PB203563 (b), respectively. Scale bar: 5 mm.

Figure S5. Phylogenetic framework of the Lycophytina sensu Kenrick et Crane (§) and the Zosterophyllopsida sensu Hao et Xue (‡). (a) Modified from figure 5.25 in ref. [3]; (b) Modified from figure 6.10 in ref. [4].

Table S1. Morphological comparisons between *Zosterophyllum baoyangense* sp. nov. and other related plants

Taxa	Erect branching	Circinate tip	Enation	Terminated sporangium	Sporangiotaxis	Orientation and stalk	Sporangial shape/valve	Thickened rim or border /junction	Age and type locality	References
<i>Anisophyton gothanii</i>	d or p	+	+spines	-	single row	upright/ss	reniform/ isovalve	??	D(Emsian)/ Germany	[5]
<i>Baoyinia sichuanensis</i>	?	?	-	+	spiral	upright/ss	ovoid/ isovalve	-/-	D(Lochkovian or early Pragian)/China	[6]
<i>Barinophyton citrulliforme</i>	p	-?	-	?	two rows	perpendicu lar/?	oval/ isovalve?	-/-	D(Famennian)/ USA	[7]
<i>Bathurstia denticulata</i>	d	+	+teeth	-	two rows	upright/se	discoïd/ isovalve	??	D(Pragian)/ Canada	[8]
<i>Crenaticaulis verruculosus</i>	d or p	+	+teeth	-	two rows	upright/ss	reniform to spherical/ anisovalve	-/-	D(Emsian)/ Canada	[9]
<i>Danziella artesiana</i>	d	-	-	?	irregular	perpendicu lar/ls	elliptical to reniform/ isovalve	+/-	D(Pragian- Emsian)/France	[10]
<i>Deheubarthia splendens</i>	d or p	+	+spines	-	two rows	upright/ss	reniform/ isovalve	??	D(Lochkovian– Pragian)/UK	[11]
<i>Discalis longistipa</i>	d	+	+spines	-	spiral	upright/ls	round/ isovalve	+/-	D(Pragian)/ China	[12]

<i>Distichophytum ovatum (Rebuchia ovata)</i>	d	-	-	-?	two rows	upright/ss	reniform/ isovalve	+/?	D(Pragian- Emsian)/USA	[13]
<i>Forania plegiospinosa</i>	d or p	+	+spines	-?	solitary	upright/ss or se	elliptical to round/ isovalve	?/?	D(Emsian)/ Canada	[14]
<i>Gippslandites minutus</i>	?	-?	-	+	spiral	upright/l	sub-circular /anisovalve	-/-	D/(Lochkovian- Pragian)/ Australia	[15]
<i>Gosslingia breconensis</i>	d or p	+	-	-	one or two rows	perpendicu lar/ss	reniform to globose/ isovalve	-/-	D(Pragian)/UK	[16]
<i>Guangnania cuneata</i>	d	-	-	-	spiral	upright/l	cuneate/ anisovalve	+/-	D(Pragian-?earl iest Emsian)/China	[17]
<i>Gumuia zyzzata</i>	d	-	-	+	irregular	perpendicu lar/se or ss	round or elliptical/ isovalve	-/-	D(Pragian)/ China	[4]
<i>Gutzeitia timanica</i>	d	-?	-	?	spiral	upright?/ss	square to oval/?	?/?	D(Frasnian)/ Russia	[18]
<i>Hicklingia edwardii</i>	d or p?	-?	-	+	spiral	upright/ss	globose/ isovalve	-/+	D(Eifelian)/ UK	[19]
<i>Konioria andrychoviensis</i>	d	+	+spines	-	below dichotomy	upright?/ss	oval to reniform/	-/-?	D(Emsian)/ Poland	[20]

<i>Macivera gracilis</i>	d	-	-	+	spiral	upright/se	elliptical/ isovalve?	+/-	S(Ludlow)/ Canada	[21]
<i>Margophyton goldschmidtii</i>	p	?	+spines	-	scarce	perpendicu lar/ss	reniform/?	?/?	D(Lochkovian– Emsian)/ Siberia	[22]
<i>Nothia aphylla</i>	d	-	+	+	spiral	upright/l _s	reniform/ isovalve	-?/?	D(Pragian)/UK	[23]
<i>Odonax borealis</i>	d	+?	+spines	?	two rows	upright/ss	reniform/ isovalve	?/?	D(Emsian)/ Belgium	[24]
<i>Omniastrabus dawsonii</i>	?	?	-?	+	two rows	perpendicu lar/?	elliptical/?	?/?	D(Emsian)/ Canada	[25]
<i>Ornicephalum sichuanense</i>	?	-?	-	?	spiral	upright/l _s	“bird’s head”/ anisovalve	-/-	D(Lochkovian or Pragian)/China	[26]
<i>Oricilla bilinearis</i>	d	+	-	-	two rows	perpendicu lar/ss	reniform/ isovalve	-/-	D(Emsian)/ Canada	[27]
<i>Parazosterophyllum timsiae</i>	p	-?	-	+?	spiral	upright/l _s	circular/ anisovalve	+/-	D(Pridoli– Pragian)/ Australia	[15]
<i>Protobarinophyton pennsylvanicum</i>	d or p	-	-	?	two rows	?/ss	oval/?	-/-	D(Famennian)/ USA	[28]
<i>Ramoferis amalia</i>	d	-	-	+	irregular , spiral	upright/l _s	ovoid to pear- shaped/ isovalve	-/+	D(Pragian)/ China	[29]

<i>Sawdonia ornata</i>	p	+	+spines	-	two rows	upright or perpendicu lar/ss	round/ anisovalve	-/-	D(Emsian)/ Canada	[30]
<i>Serrulacaulis furcatus</i>	d	+	+teeth	-	two rows	upright/ss	reniform/ isovalve	+/?	D(Frasnian)/ USA	[31]
<i>Sichuania uskielloides</i>	?	?	-	?	spiral	upright/l _s	elongate/ isovalve?	+/-	D(Lochkovian or early Pragian)/China	[6]
<i>Tarella trowenii</i>	d	+	-	-	two rows	perpendicu lar/ss	reniform/ isovalve	?/?	D(Pragian)/UK	[32]
<i>Thrinakophyton formosum</i>	d or p	+	+hairs	-	two rows	upright/ss	oval to reniform/ isovalve	+/?	D(Lochkovian or Pragian)/UK	[33]
<i>Trichopherophyton teuchansii</i>	d or p?	+	+hairs	-	?	upright/se	oval/ anisovalve	-/+?	D(Pragian)/UK	[34]
<i>Ventarura lyonii</i>	d	?	+	-?	two rows	perpendicu lar/se	circular or pear-shaped/ anisovalve	+/?	D(Pragian)/UK	[35]
<i>Wenshania zhichangensis</i>	d or p	-	-	-?	subopposite and decussate	upright/ss	reniform/ isovalve	+/+	D(Pragian)/ China	[36]
<i>Xitunia spinitheca</i>	?	?	?	?	spiral	upright/ss	wedge/ anisovalve	-/-	D(Lochkovian)/ China	[37]

<i>Zosterophyllum myretonianum</i>	d or p	-	-	+	spiral	upright/ss	reniform/ isovalve	-/+	D(Lochkovian)/ UK	[2]
<i>Zosterophyllum yunnanicum</i>	d or p	-	-	+?	spiral	upright/ss	circular to elliptical/ isovalve	+/-	D(Pragian–?earl iest Emsian)/China	[38]
<i>Zosterophyllum baoyangense</i> sp. nov.	d	-	-	+	spiral	upright/ss	oval to semicircular/ isovalve	-/-	D(Pragian)/ China	this study

Abbreviations and symbols, d: dichotomous; p, pseudomonopodial; junction, junction between sporangium and stalk; +, exist; -, absent; ?, not clear.

Table S2. Morphological comparisons among the species of *Zosterophyllum*, including *Z. baoyangense* sp. nov.

Species	Erect branching	K-or H-branching	Sporangial arrangement	Spike/fertile region	Thickened aboard/Peripheral rim	Sporangial shape in face view	Junction	Stalk	Age	Locality	References
<i>Z. qujingense</i>	d	yes	spiral or irregular	compact	strong	wedge-shaped or elliptical	-	short	S/Pridoli	China	[39]
<i>Z. fertile</i>	d	-	in two rows	loose	-	Elongate to reniform	-	short	D/Lochkovian –Emsian	UK, Belgium	[40–42]
<i>Z. xishanense</i>	d	yes	spiral	compact	narrow	round	-	short	D/Lochkovian	China	[39]
<i>Z. minorstachyum</i>	d?	yes	spiral	compact	-	elliptical or round	-	short	D/Lochkovian	China	[37]
<i>Z. shengfengense</i>	d	yes	spiral	loose	-	round to reniform	-	short	D/Lochkovian	China	[43]
<i>Z. myretonianum</i>	d or p	yes	spiral	various	narrow	reniform	-	short or long	D/Lochkovian –Emsian	UK, China	[2, 44]
<i>Z. ovatum</i> (“ <i>Z. myretonianum</i> ”)	-	-	spiral	loose	narrow	oval	+	short	D/Lochkovian –early Pragian	China	[26, 45]
<i>Z. australianum</i>	d	yes	spiral	compact	strong	elliptical to round	+	short	D/Pragian–Emsian	Australia, China	[4, 46–48]
<i>Z. ramosum</i>	d	-	spiral	compact or loose	strong	round or reniform	+	long	D/Pragian	China	[4]
<i>Z. minifertillum</i>	d	-	spiral	compact	strong	round to elliptical	+	short	D/Pragian	China	[4]
<i>Z. tenerum</i>	d	-	spiral	loose	narrow	pear-shaped	+	short	D/Pragian	China	[4]

<i>Z. minor</i>	d	-	spiral	compact	-	oval to round	-	-	D/Pragian	Siberia	[49, 50]
<i>Z. llanoveranum</i>	p?	-	in two rows	loose	narrow	Reniform to circular	-	short or long	D/Pragian	UK	[51, 52]
<i>Z. bifurcatum</i>	d	-	spiral	compact	strong?	reniform	+?	short?	D/Pragian-?earliest Emsian	China	[44]
<i>Z. yunnanicum</i>	d or p	yes	spiral	compact	strong	round to elliptical	-	short	D/Pragian-?earliest Emsian	China	[38]
<i>Z. confertum</i>	d	-	spiral	compact	narrow	Reniform to elliptical	-	short	D/Pragian-early Emsian	Germany	[53]
<i>Z. sinense</i>	d	yes	spiral	loose	-	pear-or fan-shaped	-	short or long	D/Pragian-Emsian	China	[54]
<i>Z. deciduum</i>	d or p	yes	spiral	loose	strong	reniform to oval	+	long	D/Emsian	Belgium	[55]
<i>Z. dushanense</i>	-	-	spiral	loose	-	wedge-shaped	-	short?	D/Emsian	China	[44]
<i>Z. divaricatum</i>	d	-	in two rows	loose	-	reniform	-	short	D/Emsian	Canada	[56]
<i>Z. spectabile</i>	d	-	in two rows	loose	-	reniform	-	short	D/Emsian	Germany	[57]
<i>Z. rhenanum</i>	d	yes	spiral	loose	strong	reniform to elliptical	+	short	D/Lochkovian-Emsian	Germany	[57–59]
<i>Z. baoyangense</i> sp. nov.	d	yes	spiral	compact	narrow	round	-	short	D/Pragian	China	this work

Abbreviations and symbols: d, dichotomous; p, pseudomonopodial; junction, junction between sporangium and stalk; S, Silurian; D, Devonian; +, exist; -, absent or not clear.

Table S3. Morphological measurements of *Zosterophyllum* species from the late Silurian to Early Devonian periods

Species	Axis (mm)*		Spike/fertile region			Sporangia (mm)		TSA (Total sporangial accommodation) (mm ³)	Age	Locality	References
	Length**	Width	Number of Sporangia ***	Length (mm)	Width (mm)	Height	Width				
<i>Zosterophyllum</i> sp. (I)	31.4†	1.0	> 27	> 31.4†	6.6†	1.1–1.7	1.9–2.1	33.9–57.8	S/Ludlow	Bathurst Island, Canada	[21]
<i>Z. qujingense</i> (II)	53.0	0.7–1.4	3–8	7.4–17.6	3.7–4.5	2.5–4.5	3.1–4.7	14.0–101.5	S/Pridoli	Qujing, China	[39]
<i>Z. fertile</i> (I)	72.0	2.8–3.0	> 30	> 72.0	4.1–5.1†	2.5–3.8	2.3–3.0	103.5–205.2	D/Lochkovian	Forfar, Scotland	[41]
<i>Z. xishanense</i> (III)	116.0	0.7–1.9	6–10	7.8–14.2	3.4–5.2	2.0–4.1	2.2–3.5	15.8–86.1	D/Lochkovian	Qujing, China	[39]
<i>Z. fertile?</i> (<i>Zosterophyllum</i> sp.) (I)	35.0	1.0–2.7	> 14	> 35.0	-	1.3–2.8	0.8–2.0	8.7–47.0	D/Lochkovian	Shropshire, UK	[60, 61]
<i>Z. fertile</i> (I)	30.0	1.0–1.3†	> 18	> 30.0	3.0	2.0	1.8–2.0	38.9–43.2	D/Lochkovian	Belgium	[40]
# <i>Z. cf. fertile</i> (I)	28.7†	1.5–1.8	> 11	> 20.0	3.5	1.6–2.8	2.3–2.8	24.3–51.7	D/Lochkovian	Newport, Wales	[61, 62]
<i>Z. minorstachyum</i> (II)	61.0	0.7–1.9	17	9.4–11.6	1.2–3.2	1.0–1.4	1.2–2.0	12.2–28.6	D/Lochkovian	Qujing, China	[37]
<i>Z. shengfengense</i> (III)	98.0	0.5–1.5	> 9†	24.4–43.0†	3.4–3.9†	1.4–1.9	1.7–2.9	12.9–29.8	D/Lochkovian	Qujing, China	[43]
<i>Z. myretonianum</i> (I) (PB6429)	20.0	0.9	9–10	> 20.0	3.0	1.8	1.6	15.6–17.3	D/Lochkovian	Qujing, China	[44]
<i>Z. myretonianum</i> (III)	200.0	0.9–3.0	11–22	45.0–100.0	-	1.7–4.2	2.7–5.0	30.3–277.2	D/Lochkovian	Scotland, UK	[2, 63]

# <i>Z. ovatum</i> (“ <i>Z. myretonianum</i> ”) (I)	80.0	ca 1.5	7–9	> 27.0†	4.0†	2.5–3.8	3.6–5.2	37.8–106.7	D/Lochkovian–early Pragian	Jiangyou, China	[26, 45]
<i>Z. rhenanum</i> (I?)	-	2.6†	26†	40.0–50.0	9.8†	4.0–5.0	5.0–6.0	312.0–468.0	D/Lochkovian–early Emsian	Rhineland, Germany	[57]
<i>Z. baoyangense</i> sp. nov. (II)	45.4	0.5–1.3	5–10	5.8–10.8	2.0–2.8	1.6–2.0	0.9–1.4	4.3–16.8	D/Pragian	Duyun, China	this work
<i>Z. australianum</i> (I)	141.0	2.0	22	16.2	4.5	3.9	2.6–4.1	133.8–211.1	D/Pragian	Duyun, China	[48]
“ <i>Z. cf. australianum</i> ” (I)	28.0†	2.0–3.0	> 12? †	8.0–12.0	4.0–7.0	4.0	2.0–5.0	57.6–144.0	D/Pragian	Llanover Quarry, UK	[51]
<i>Z. australianum</i> (I)	110.0	1.0–2.8	12–15	13.0–15.2	4.3–6.8	2.6–3.6	3.5–4.5	65.5–145.8	D/Pragian	Wenshan, China	[4, 47]
<i>Z. ramosum</i> (I)	153.0	1.3–3.0	8–15	13.0–26.0	4.0–8.0	1.9–5.5	1.6–6.0	14.6–297.0	D/Pragian	Wenshan, China	[47]
<i>Z. minifertillum</i> (I)	72.0	0.6–1.3	6–17	7.2–20.0	3.0–3.8	1.4–3.0	1.8–3.6	9.1–110.2	D/Pragian	Wenshan, China	[4]
# <i>Z. tenerum</i> (II)	129.0	0.4–2.1	25	> 112.0†	2.8–7.5†	1.9–3.1	1.2–2.9	34.2–134.9	D/Pragian	Wenshan, China	[4]
# <i>Z. cf. fertile</i> (I)	95.0	0.8–2.5	> 8	> 10.0	3.0	1.7–2.5	1.6–2.0	13.1–24.0	D/Pragian	Wales, UK	[64]
<i>Z. llanoveranum</i> (I)	200.0	0.8–2.5	> 12	> 90.0	-	4.0	3.5	100.8	D/Pragian	Wales, UK	[51, 52]
# <i>Z. rhenanum</i> (II)	103.0†	1.0	5–20†	20.0–50.0	5.0–8.0	3.5–4.7†	2.5–4.0	26.3–225.6	D/Pragian	Rhineland, Germany	[58]
# <i>Z. cf. myretonianum</i> (<i>Z. longhuashanense</i>) (I)	35.0	1.8	12	> 35.0	7.0	2.2–3.1	1.3–2.8	20.6–62.5	D/Pragian–?earliest Emsian	Qujing, China	[65]
# <i>Z. bifurcatum</i> (I)	9.6†	1.0	7–8	> 9.6†	3.3†	1.9–2.3	3.0–4.4	23.9–48.6	D/Pragian–?earliest Emsian	Qujing, China	[44]
<i>Z. australianum</i> (I)	140.0	1.0–4.0	8–30	9.5–31.8	4.5–8.9	2.2–4.4	2.8–6.3	29.6–499.0	D/Pragian–?earliest Emsian	Qujing, China	[66]

<i>Z. yunnanicum</i> (II)	100.0	0.5–2.7	8–27†	30.0–50.0	4.0–6.0	1.0–3.3	1.2–4.8	5.8–256.6	D/Pragian–?earliest Emsian)	Qujing, China	[38, 67, 68]
<i>Z. confertum</i> (I)	440.0	1.0–5.1	6–18	5.0–23.0	3.0–12.0	6.0	7.0	151.2–453.6	D/Pragian–early Emsian	Rhenish Massif, Germany	[53]
<i>Z. sinense</i> (III)	250.0	1.2–2.0	10–28	21.1–43.2	3.9–6.8	2.4–4.7	2.5–3.2	36.0–252.7	D/Pragian–Emsian	Cangwu, China	[54]
<i>Z. deciduum</i> (II)	50.0	0.3–1.3	25†	35.0†	1.8–2.0†	0.7–1.8	0.7–2.4	7.4–64.8	D/Emsian	Marchin, Belgium	[55]
# <i>Z. dushanense</i> (I)	14.0	1.2	> 9†	> 14.0	9.0	5.5	4.0	118.8	D/Emsian	Dushan, China	[44]
<i>Z. yunnanicum</i> (I)	29.0	1.2–1.5	11	16.0	2.0–4.5	4.3–5.0	3.0	85.1–99.0	D/Emsian	Dushan, China	[44]
# <i>Z. divaricatum</i> (I)	140.0	1.0–4.0	5–14†	> 73.5†	3.0–7.3†	2.0–4.0	2.0–4.0	12.0–134.4	D/Emsian	New Brunswick, Canada	[56]
<i>Z. spectabile</i> (I)	-	2.5	20	50.0	-	3.5–4.0	3.5	147.0–168.0	D/Emsian	Rhineland, Germany	[57]
<i>Z. australianum</i> (I)	40.0	1.5–5.0	6–7	13.0–20.0	4.5–12.0	4.0 or 5.0?	3.0–8.0	43.2–168.0	D/Emsian	Victoria, Australia	[46]

Notes: *including measurements of both sterile and fertile axes; **, length of the longest preserved axis; ***, number of visible sporangia of the longest preserved spike; †, based on published illustrations; #, obviously incomplete spike or fertile region; I, II, and III, three different preservation conditions (see material and methods for details); S, Silurian; D, Devonian.

Table S4. Morphological measurements of the members of the Lycopytina sensu Kenrick et Crane and the Zosterophyllopsida sensu Hao et Xue from late Silurian to Early Devonian

Taxa	Axis (mm)*		Spike/fertile region			Sporangia (mm)		TSA (Total sporangial accommodation) (mm ³)	Age	Locality	References
	Length**	Width	Number of Sporangia***	Length (mm)	Width (mm)	Height	Width				
<i>Distichophytum</i> sp. (§, ‡)	> 42.0†	1.1–1.2	10–14	8.2–10.0	2.2–3.8	1.4–2.1	1.2–1.9	10.1–33.5	S/Ludlow	Bathurst Island, Canada	[21]
<i>Macivera gracilis</i> (‡)	> 81.0	0.1–1.0	2–10	2.5–5.5	17.9–31.8†	1.3–2.0	1.1–1.3	1.7–15.6	S/Ludlow	Bathurst Island, Canada	[21]
<i>Baragwanathia brevifolioides</i> (B. <i>brevifolia</i>) (§)	> 95.0	2.5–4.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	S/Pridoli	Bohemia, Czech Republic	[69]
<i>Baragwanathia longifolia</i> (§)	> 280.0	10.0–20.0	-	-	-	< 2.0	2.0	-	S/Pridoli	Victoria, Australia	[70]
<i>Parazosterophyllum timsiae</i> (‡)	> 57.9†	1.2–4.2	9	17.0	9.5	1.6–3.5	1.7–3.5	14.7–66.2	S–D/Pridoli–Pragian	Victoria, Australia	[15]
# <i>Xitunia spinitheca</i> (‡)	> 21.0	-	> 11	> 21.0	9.6–11.2	2.9–5.2	2.6–4.8	49.8–164.7	D/Lochkovian	Qujing, China	[37]
# <i>Adoketophyton pingyipuensis</i> (§)	> 38.0	0.9†	> 15	> 38.0	5.9–8.5†	0.9–1.9	0.7–0.9	5.7–15.4	D/Lochkovian or early Pragian	Jiangyou, China	[26]
# <i>Baoyinia sichuanensis</i> (‡)	> 70.0	2.0–3.0	> 6†	51.3†	6.4–7.7†	4.0–7.5	2.5–3.5	36.0–94.5	D/Lochkovian or early Pragian	Jiangyou, China	[6]

# <i>Ornicephalum sichuanense</i> (‡)	> 60.0	0.5–1.7	> 6	19.0	7.3†	1.5–2.7	1.6–2.8	8.6–27.2	D/Lochkovian or early Pragian	Jiangyou, China	[6]
# <i>Sichuania uskielloides</i> (‡)	> 60.0	1.2–2.3	> 4	> 60.0	4.3†	4.0–6.0	2.8–4.8	26.9–69.1	D/Lochkovian or early Pragian	Jiangyou, China	[26]
<i>Deheubarthia splendens</i> (§, ‡)	> 300.0	1.2–11.0	-	-	-	2.9–5.8	5.0	-	D/Lochkovian–Pragian	South Wales, UK	[11]
<i>Gippslandites minutus</i> (‡)	> 7.5	0.3	9	6.0	6.7	0.3–1.9	0.6–2.6	1.0–26.7	D/Lochkovian–Pragian	Victoria, Australia	[15]
<i>Gosslingia breconensis</i> (§, ‡)	> 150.0	0.5–4.0	-	-	-	1.7–2.5	0.9–2.2	-	D/Lochkovian–Pragian	South Wales, UK	[16]
# <i>Guangnania minor</i> (‡)	> 155.0	0.6–1.6	> 8†	> 30.0	1.9–3.5†	1.7–3.2	1.2–1.9	9.8–29.2	D/Lochkovian–Pragian	Jiangyou, China	[71]
<i>Sengelia radicans</i> (§)	> 250.0	3.0–34.0	-	-	-	2.3–3.7	2.3–3.7	-	D/late Lochkovian–early Pragian	Wyoming, USA	[72]
<i>Adoketophyton subverticillatum</i> (§)	> 90.0	0.9–2.6	27	> 90.0	6.7–13.5†	1.5–2.7	2.0–3.2	48.6–140.0	D/Pragian	Wenshan, China	[73]
<i>Adoketophyton parvulum</i> (§)	> 85.0	0.4–1.7	30	7.0–17.0	2.2–2.8	0.7–1.1	0.8–1.5	10.1–29.7	D/Pragian	Wenshan, China	[74]
<i>Asteroxylon mackiei</i> (§)	-	2.0–12.0	-	-	-	1.7–15.2	0.6–5.6	-	D/Pragian	Scotland, UK	[75]
<i>Bathurstia denticulata</i> (‡)	300.0	4.0–12.0	36†	28.0–80.0	7.0–18.0	2.5–8.0	2.1–5.0	113.4–864.0	D/Pragian	Bathurst Island, Canada	[8]
# <i>Discalis longistipa</i> (§, ‡)	> 150.0	3.2–5.0	> 10†	31.2†	7.8†	3.2–4.3	3.2–4.3	61.4–110.9	D/Pragian	Wenshan, China	[4, 12]

<i>Gumuiia zyzzata</i> (§, ‡)	> 120.0	0.5–4.0	6–11	30.0–37.0	8.9–9.7†	1.8–5.0	2.0–7.0	13.0–231.0	D/Pragian	Wenshan, China	[76]
<i>Huia recurvata</i> (§)	> 175.0	5.0–14.0	3–9	65.0	18.0	2.7–10.0	1.6–5.0	7.8–270.0	D/Pragian	Wenshan, China	[77]
<i>Nothia aphylla</i> (§, ‡)	-	1.0–3.3	-	-	-	1.5	3.0	-	D/Pragian	Scotland, UK	[23]
<i>Ramoferis amalia</i> (‡)	> 116.0	3.0–5.2	12–19	8.0–48.0	6.2–9.3	2.5–5.0	3.0–6.4	54.0–364.8	D/Pragian	Wenshan, China	[4, 29]
<i>Sawdonia ornata</i> (§, ‡)	-	5.0	-	-	-	-	3.0–3.5	-	D/Pragian	Gaspé, Canada	[78]
<i>Tarella trowenii</i> (§, ‡)	-	2.8–8.2	-	-	-	1.5–3.0	2.2–4.0	-	D/Pragian	Wales, UK	[32]
<i>Thrinophyton formosum</i> (§, ‡)	> 90.0	0.5–2.8	13†	20.0	-	1.0–1.3	1.8–2.2	14.0–22.3	D/Pragian	Wales, UK	[33]
<i>Trichopherophyton teuchansii</i> (§, ‡)	-	2.5	-	-	-	2.3–2.5	3.0–3.8	-	D/Pragian	Scotland, UK	[34]
<i>Ventarura lyonii</i> (§, ‡)	> 120.0	3.6–7.2	-	-	-	3.5–4.0	4.0–5.2	-	D/Pragian	Scotland, UK	[35]
# <i>Wenshania zhichangensis</i> (‡)	> 34.0†	3.1	> 8	> 34.0†	-	2.0–9.8	1.8–8.3	17.3–390.4	D/Pragian	Wenshan, China	[36]
<i>Drepanophycus qujingensis</i> (§)	> 300.0	5.0–25.0	-	-	-	3.0–4.5	2.5–5.0	-	D/Pragian–?earliest Emsian	Qujing, China	[79]
# <i>Guangnania cuneata</i> (‡)	> 80.0	0.6–3.0	14	50.0–73.0	3.5–7.0	3.5–9.6	1.2–2.8	35.3–225.8	D/Pragian–?earliest Emsian	Qujing, China	[17]
<i>Hsüa deflexa</i> (§)	> 128.0	0.3–13.0	-	-	-	1.3–3.2	1.3–5.0	-	D/Pragian–?earliest Emsian	Qujing, China	[80]

<i>Hsüa robusta</i> (§)	> 240.0	1.5–10.0	-	-	-	0.8–4.2	1.0–8.2	-	D/Pragian–?earliest Emsian	Qujing, China	[81]
<i>Huia gracilis</i> (§, ‡)	> 210.0	0.8–8.6	21	41.0–100.0	5.0–16.0	1.9–7.5	1.0–5.2	23.9–491.4	D/Pragian–?earliest Emsian	Qujing, China	[82]
<i>Danziella artesiana</i> (<i>Zosterophyllum artesianum</i>) (‡)	> 85.0	1.5	-	-	-	1.3–2.1	1.6–3.0	-	D/Pragian–Emsian	northern France	[10]
# <i>Distichophytum mucronatum</i> (§, ‡)	> 30.0†	1.0†	7†	> 30.0†	3.5†	3.0–4.0	1.5–2.0	18.9–33.6	D/Pragian–Emsian	Harz, Germany	[50]
<i>Distichophytum ovatum</i> (§, ‡)	> 85.0	1.5–2.0	11–20	18.0–32.0	4.7–4.9†	2.5–3.0	2.1–3.0	34.7–108.0	D/Pragian–Emsian	Wyoming, USA	[13]
<i>Drepanophycus qujingensis</i> (<i>Drepanophycus spinaeformis</i>) (§)	> 130.0	2.0–30.0	-	-	-	2.5	2.5	-	D/Pragian–Emsian	Guizhou, China	[83]
<i>Anisophyton gothanii</i> (§, ‡)	> 280.0	3.0–5.5	-	-	-	1.5–1.7	2.0–2.3	-	D/Emsian	Germany	[5]
<i>Baragwanathia abitibiensis</i> (§)	> 108.6†	6.0–32.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	D/Emsian	Ontario, Canada	[84]
<i>Barinophyton robustius</i> (<i>Pectinophyton bipectinatum</i>) (§)	> 317.1†	1.5–8.5†	16†	25.5–30.4†	9.9†	3.8–6.8†	3.8–6.8†	138.6–443.9	D/Emsian	Torgashino, Siberia	[50]
<i>Crenaticaulis verruculosus</i> (§, ‡)	> 220.0	1.0–3.0	-	-	-	2.0	2.0	-	D/Emsian	Quebec, Canada	[9]

<i>Drepanophycus spinaeformis</i> (§)	> 200.0	10.0–21.0	-	-	-	3.0–5.0	3.0–5.0	-	D/Emsian	New Brunswick, Canada	[85]
<i>Forania plegiospinosa</i> (‡)	> 200.0	3.0–10.0	-	-	-	1.0	1.0–2.0	-	D/Emsian	New Brunswick, Canada	[14]
<i>Konioria andrychoviensis</i> (§, ‡)	> 150.0	0.3–4.0	-	-	-	0.5–2.5	0.5–2.5	-	D/Emsian	Poland	[20]
<i>Odonax borealis</i> (‡)	> 830.0	1.1–2.7	> 8†	35.0	3.0–5.0	2.0–3.7	1.5–4.0	14.4–71.0	D/Emsian	Belgium	[24]
<i>Oricilla bilinearis</i> (§, ‡)	> 120.0	3.0–5.0	-	-	-	1.0–3.0	2.0–4.0	-	D/Emsian	New Brunswick, Canada	[27]
<i>Protobarinophyton obrutschevii</i> (§)	> 300.0	7.0	26†	15.0–37.0	7.0–12.0	1.5	5.0	117.0	D/Emsian	Siberia	[50]
<i>Sawdonia acanthotheca</i> (§, ‡)	> 180.0	3.0–8.0	-	-	-	4.0	4.0	-	D/Emsian	New Brunswick, Canada	[86]
<i>Sawdonia ornata</i> (§, ‡)	-	1.6–2.6	-	-	-	1.4–3.4	1.7–4.0	-	D/Emsian	Gaspé Bay, Canada	[87]

Notes: *, including measurements of both sterile and fertile axes; **, length of the longest preserved axis; ***, number of visible sporangia of the longest preserved spike; †, based on published illustrations; #, obviously incomplete spike or fertile region; §, taxa within in Lycophytina sensu Kenrick et Crane; ‡, taxa within the Zosterophyllopsida sensu Hao et Xue; -, not available; S, Silurian; D, Devonian.

References

1. Huang P, Liu L, Xue JZ. 2022 A new polysporangiate land plant with novel fertile organs from the Lower Devonian of Guizhou, southwestern China. *Rev. Palaeobot. Palynol.* **302**, 104661. (doi: 10.1016/j.revpalbo.2022.104661)
2. Edwards D. 1975 Some observations on the fertile parts of *Zosterophyllum myretonianum* Penhallow from the Lower Old Red Sandstone of Scotland. *Trans. R. Soc. Edinb.* **69**, 251–265. (doi: 10.1017/s0080456800015209)
3. Kenrick P, Crane PR. 1997 *The origin and early diversification of land plants, a cladistic study*. Washington: Smithsonian Institution Press.
4. Hao SG, Xue JZ. 2013 *The Early Devonian Posongchong flora of Yunnan*. Beijing: Science Press.
5. Remy W, Schultak S, Hass H. 1986 *Anisophyton gothani* nov. gen. et nov. spec., und Hinweise zur Stratigraphie der siidlichen Wilbringhauser Scholle. *Argumenta Palaeobotanica* **7**, 79–107.
6. Edwards D, Li CS. 2018 Further insights into the Lower Devonian terrestrial vegetation of Sichuan Province, China. *Rev. Palaeobot. Palynol.* **253**, 37–48. (doi: 10.1016/j.revpalbo.2018.03.004)
7. Brauer DF. 1980 *Barinophyton citrulliforme* (Barinophytales Incertae Sedis, Barinophytaceae) from the Upper Devonian of Pennsylvania. *Am. J. Bot.* **67**, 1186–1206. (doi: 10.2307/2442362)
8. Kotyk ME, Basinger JF. 2000 The Early Devonian (Pragian) zosterophyll *Bathurstia denticulata* Hueber. *Can. J. Bot.* **78**, 193–207. (doi: 10.1139/b99-179)
9. Banks HP, Davis MR. 1969 *Crenaticaulis*, a new genus of Devonian plants allied to *Zosterophyllum*, and its bearing on the classification of early land plants. *Am. J. Bot.* **56**, 436–449. (doi: 10.2307/2440821)
10. Edwards D. 2006 *Danziella artesiana*, a new name for *Zosterophyllum artesianum* from the Lower Devonian of Artois, northern France. *Rev. Palaeobot. Palynol.* **142**, 93–101. (doi: 10.1016/j.revpalbo.2006.04.008)
11. Edwards D, Kenrick P, Carluccio LM. 1989 A reconsideration of cf. *Psilophyton princeps* (Croft & Lang, 1942), a zosterophyll widespread in the Lower Old Red Sandstone of South Wales. *Bot. J. Linn. Soc.* **100**, 293–318. (doi: 10.1111/j.1095-8339.1989.tb01723.x)
12. Hao SG. 1989 A new zosterophyll from the Lower Devonian (Siegenian) of Yunnan, China. *Rev. Palaeobot. Palynol.* **57**, 155–171. (doi:

- 10.1016/0034-6667(89)90018-3)
13. Hueber FM. 1972 *Rebuchia ovata*, its vegetative morphology and classification with the Zosterophyllophytina. *Rev. Palaeobot. Palynol.* **14**, 113–127. (doi: 10.1016/0034-6667(72)90012-7)
 14. Jensen DP, Gensel PG. 2013 *Forania plegiospinosa*, gen. et sp. nov.: a zosterophyll from the Early Devonian of New Brunswick, Canada, with a novel emergence type. *Int. J. Plant. Sci.* **174**, 687–701. (doi: 10.1086/669914)
 15. McSweeney FR, Shimeta J, Buckeridge JS. 2020 Two new genera of early Tracheophyta (Zosterophyllaceae) from the upper Silurian–Lower Devonian of Victoria, Australia. *Alcheringa* **44**, 379–396. (doi: 10.1080/03115518.2020.1744725)
 16. Edwards D. 1970 Further observations on the Lower Devonian plant, *Gosslingia breconensis* Heard. *Philos. Trans. R. Soc. Lond., B, Biol. Sci.* **258**, 225–243. (doi: 10.1098/rstb.1970.0034)
 17. Wang DM, Hao SG. 2002 *Guangnania cuneata* gen. et sp. nov. from the Lower Devonian of Yunnan Province, China. *Rev. Palaeobot. Palynol.* **122**, 13–27. (doi: 10.1016/s0034-6667(02)00089-1)
 18. Snigirevsky SM, Tschibrikova EV, Olli VA. 2007 Fossil plants with spores in the sporangia from the Upper Devonian (Frasnian) deposits of northern Timan. *Paleontol. J.* **41**, 461–468. (doi: 10.1134/s0031030107040120)
 19. Edwards D. 1976 The systematic position of *Hicklingia edwardii* Kidston and Lang. *New Phytol.* **76**, 173–181. (doi: 10.1111/j.1469-8137.1976.tb01449.x)
 20. Zdebska D. 1982 A new zosterophyll from the Lower Devonian of Poland. *Palaeontology* **25**, 247–263.
 21. Kotyk ME, Basinger JF, Gensel PG, de Freitas TA. 2002 Morphologically complex plant macrofossils from the Late Silurian of Arctic Canada. *Am. J. Bot.* **89**, 1004–1013. (doi: 10.3732/ajb.89.6.1004)
 22. Zakharova TV. 1981 On the systematic position of the species *Psilophyton goldschmidtii* from the Lower Devonian of Eurasia. *Paleontol. J.* **15**, 109–118.
 23. Kerp H, Hass H, Mosbrugger V. 2001 New data on *Nothia aphylla* Lyon 1964 ex El-Saadawy et Lacey 1979, a poorly known plant form from the Lower Devonian Rhynie Chert. In *Plants invade the land*. (eds PG Gensel and D Edwards), pp. 52–82. New York: Columbia University Press.
 24. Gerrienne P. 1996 Lower Devonian plant remains from Marchin (northern margin of Dinant Synclinorium, Belgium). IV. *Odonax borealis* gen. et sp. nov. *Rev. Palaeobot. Palynol.* **93**, 89–106. (doi: 10.1016/0034-6667(95)00121-2)

25. Bonacorsi NK, Gensel PG, Hueber FM, Leslie AB. 2021 *Omniastrobus* gen. nov., an Emsian plant with implications for the evolution of heterospory in the Early Devonian. *Int. J. Plant Sci.* **182**, 198–209. (doi: 10.1086/712356)
26. Edwards D, Li CS. 2018 Diversity in affinities of plants with lateral sporangia from the Lower Devonian of Sichuan Province, China. *Rev. Palaeobot. Palynol.* **258**, 98–111. (doi: 10.1016/j.revpalbo.2018.07.002)
27. Gensel PG. 1982 *Oricilla*, a new genus referable to the zosterophyllophytes from the late Early Devonian of northern New Brunswick. *Rev. Palaeobot. Palynol.* **37**, 345–359. (doi: 10.1016/0034-6667(82)90007-0)
28. Brauer DF. 1981 Heterosporous, barinophytacean plants from the Upper Devonian of North America and a discussion of the possible affinities of the barinophytaceae. *Rev. Palaeobot. Palynol.* **33**, 347–362. (doi: 10.1016/0034-6667(81)90092-0)
29. Hao SG, Xue JZ. 2011 A new zosterophyll plant, *Ramofervis* gen. nov., from the Posongchong Formation of Lower Devonian (Pragian) of Southeastern Yunnan, China. *Acta Geol. Sin.* **85**, 765–776. (doi: 10.1111/j.1755-6724.2011.00482.x)
30. Gensel PG, Berry CM. 2016 Sporangial morphology of the Early Devonian zosterophyll *Sawdonia ornata* from the type locality (Gaspé). *Int. J. Plant Sci.* **177**, 618–632. (doi: 10.1086/687301)
31. Hueber FM, Banks HP. 1979 *Serrulacaulis furcatus* gen. sp. nov., a new zosterophyll from the lower Upper Devonian of New York State. *Rev. Palaeobot. Palynol.* **28**, 169–189. (doi: 10.1016/0034-6667(79)90008-3)
32. Edwards D, Kenrick P. 1986 A new zosterophyll from the Lower Devonian of Wales. *Bot. J. Linn. Soc.* **92**, 269–283. (doi: 10.1111/j.1095-8339.1986.tb01432.x)
33. Kenrick P, Edwards D. 1988 A new zosterophyll from a recently discovered exposure of the Lower Devonian Senni Beds in Dyfed, Wales. *Bot. J. Linn. Soc.* **98**, 97–115. (doi: 10.1111/j.1095-8339.1988.tb01698.x)
34. Lyon AG, Edwards D. 1991 The first zosterophyll from the Lower Devonian Rhynie Chert, Aberdeenshire. *Trans. R. Soc. Edinb. Earth Sci.* **82**, 323–332. (doi: 10.1017/s0263593300004193)
35. Powell CL, Edwards D, Trewin NH. 2000 A new vascular plant from the Lower Devonian Windyfield chert, Rhynie, NE Scotland. *Trans. R. Soc. Edinb. Earth Sci.* **90**, 331–349. (doi: 10.1017/s0263593300002662)
36. Zhu WQ, Kenrick P. 1999 A *Zosterophyllum*-like plant from the Lower Devonian of Yunnan Province, China. *Rev. Palaeobot. Palynol.* **105**, 111–118. (doi: 10.1016/s0034-6667(98)00070-0)
37. Xue JZ. 2009 Two zosterophyll plants from the Lower Devonian (Lochkovian) Xitun Formation of Northeastern Yunnan, China. *Acta Geol.*

- Sin.* **83**, 504–512. (doi: 10.1111/j.1755-6724.2009.00057.x)
38. Edwards D, Yang N, Hueber FM, Li CS. 2015 Additional observations on *Zosterophyllum yunnanicum* Hsü from the Lower Devonian of Yunnan, China. *Rev. Palaeobot. Palynol.* **221**, 220–229. (doi: 10.1016/j.revpalbo.2015.03.007)
 39. Hao SG, Xue JZ, Liu ZF, Wang DM. 2007 *Zosterophyllum* Penhallow around the Silurian-Devonian boundary of Northeastern Yunnan, China. *Int. J. Plant. Sci.* **168**, 477–489. (doi: 10.1086/511011)
 40. Leclercq S. 1942 Quelques plantes fossiles recueillies dans le Dévonien inférieur des environs de Nonceveux (Bordure orientale du bassin de Dinant). *Ann. Soc. Geol. Belg.* **65**, 193–211.
 41. Edwards D. 1972 A *Zosterophyllum* fructification from the Lower Old Red Sandstone of Scotland. *Rev. Palaeobot. Palynol.* **14**, 77–83. (doi: 10.1016/0034-6667(72)90009-7)
 42. Gerrienne P. 1993 Inventaire des végétaux éodévoniens de Belgique. *Ann. Soc. Géol. Belg.* **116**, 105–117.
 43. Hao SG, Xue JZ, Guo DL, Wang DM. 2010 Earliest rooting system and root: shoot ratio from a new *Zosterophyllum* plant. *New Phytol.* **185**, 217–225. (doi: 10.1111/j.1469-8137.2009.03056.x)
 44. Li XX, Cai CY. 1977 Early Devonian *Zosterophyllum*-remains from southwest China. *Acta Palaeontol. Sin.* **16**, 12–34.
 45. Geng BY. 1992 Studies on Early Devonian flora of Sichuan. *Acta Phytotax. Sin.* **30**, 197–211.
 46. Lang WH, Cookson IC. 1931 Some fossil plants of early Devonian type from the Walhalla Series, Victoria, Australia. *Philos. Trans. R. Soc. Lond. B* **219**, 133–163. (doi: 10.1098/rstb.1931.0003)
 47. Hao SG, Wang DM. 2000 Two species of *Zosterophyllum* Penhallow (*Z. australianum* Lang and Cookson, *Z. ramosum* sp. nov.) from the Lower Devonian (Pragian) of southeastern Yunnan, China. *Acta Palaeontol. Sin.* **39**, 26–41.
 48. Zhou ZQ, Zhao JY, Wang JS, Wu CY, Xiao B, Huang P. 2022 New material of *Zosterophyllum australianum* from the Lower Devonian Mangshan Group in Duyun, Guizhou and its palaeogeographic implications. *J. Palaeogeogr (Chinese Edition)*. **24**: 479–492. (doi: 10.7605/gdlsx.2022.03.049)
 49. Ananiev AR. 1960 Thelomophyta. The highest plants. In *Paleozoic biostratigraphy of the Altai-Sayan mountain area* (ed LL Khalphin), pp. 578–599, Novosibirsk.
 50. Høeg OA. 1967 Psilophyta. In *Traité de Paléobotanique II* (ed E Boureau), pp. 362–399, Paris: Masson and Cie.
 51. Croft WN, Lang WH. 1942 The Lower Devonian flora of the Senni Beds of Monmouthshire and Breconshire. *Philos. Trans. R. Soc. Lond. B*

- 231**, 131–163. (doi: 10.1098/rstb.1942.0001)
52. Edwards D. 1969 Further observations on *Zosterophyllum llanoveranum* from the Lower Devonian of South Wales. *Am. J. Bot.* **56**, 201–210. (doi: 10.1002/j.1537-2197.1969.tb07524.x)
53. Gossmann R, Poschmann MJ, Giesen P, Schultka S. 2022 A stratigraphically significant new zosterophyllopid from the Rhenish Lower Devonian (W Germany). *Palaeobiodivers. Palaeoenviron.* **102**, 503–519. (doi: 10.1007/s12549-021-00509-9)
54. Wang Y, Xu HH, Wang Y, Qiang F. 2018 A further study of *Zosterophyllum sinense* Li and Cai (Zosterophyllopsida) based on the type and the new specimens from the Lower Devonian of Guangxi, southwestern China. *Rev. Palaeobot. Palynol.* **258**, 112–122. (doi: 10.1016/j.revpalbo.2018.05.008)
55. Gerrienne P. 1988 Early Devonian plant remains from Marchin (North of Dinant Synclinorium, Belgium) *Zosterophyllum deciduum* sp. nov. *Rev. Palaeobot. Palynol.* **55**, 317–335. (doi: 10.1016/0034-6667(88)90091-7)
56. Gensel PG. 1982 A new species of *Zosterophyllum* from the Early Devonian of New Brunswick. *Am. J. Bot.* **69**, 651–669. (doi: 10.1002/j.1537-2197.1982.tb13305.x)
57. Schweitzer HJ. 1979 Die Zosterophyllaceae des rheinischen Unterdevons. *Bonner Paläobotanische Mitteilungen* **3**, 1–32.
58. Kräusel R, Weyland H. 1935 Neue Pflanzenfunde im Rheinischen Unterdevon. *Palaeontogr. Abt. B* **80**, 171–190.
59. Cai CY, Schweitzer HJ. 1983 Über *Zosterophyllum yunnanicum* Hsü aus dem Unterdevons Sudchinas. *Palaeontogr. Abt. B* **185**, 1–10.
60. Edwards D, Richardson JB. 1974 Lower Devonian (Dittonian) plants from the Welsh Borderland. *Palaeontology* **17**, 331–324.
61. Edwards D, Wellman, CH. 2001 Embryophytes on land: The Ordovician to Lochkovian (Lower Devonian) record. In *Plant invade the land* (eds Gensel PG and Edwards D), pp. 3–28. New York: Columbia University Press.
62. Wellman CH, Habgood K, Jenkins G, Richardson JB. 2000 A new plant assemblage (microfossil and megafossil) from the Lower Old Red Sandstone of the Anglo–Welsh Basin: its implications for the palaeoecology of early terrestrial ecosystems. *Rev. Palaeobot. Palynol.* **109**, 161–196. (doi: 10.1016/s0034-6667(99)00052-4)
63. Lang WH. 1927 Contributions to the study of the Old red Sandstone flora of Scotland. VI. On *Zosterophyllum myretonianum*, Penh., and some other plant remains from the Carmyllie Beds of the Lower Old Red Sandstone. *Trans. R. Soc. Edinb.* **55**, 443–455. (doi: 10.1017/s0080456800016422)
64. Edwards D. 1969 *Zosterophyllum* from Lower Old Red Sandstone of South Wales. *New Phytol.* **68**, 923–931. (doi: 10.1111/j.1469-

8137.1969.tb06491.x)

65. Wang Y, Xu HH. 2018 New observations on the specimen attributed to *Zosterophyllum longhuashanense* from the Lower Devonian of Qujing, Yunnan, Southwestern China. *Acta Palaeontol. Sin.* **57**, 66–73. (doi: 10.19800/j.cnki.aps.2018.01.006).
66. Hao SG. 1992 Some observations on *Zosterophyllum australianum* Land & Cookson from the Lower Devonian of Yunnan, China. *Bot. J. Linn. Soc.* **109**, 189–202. (doi: 10.1111/j.1095-8339.1992.tb00265.x)
67. Hao SG. 1985 Further observations on *Zosterophyllum yunnanicum* Hsü. *Acta Bot. Sin.* **27**, 545–549.
68. Wang DM. 2007 Two species of *Zosterophyllum* from South China and dating of the Xujiachong Formation with a biostratigraphic method. *Acta Geol. Sin.* **81**, 525–538. (doi: 10.1111/j.1755-6724.2007.tb00976.x)
69. Kraft P, Kvaček Z. 2017 Where the lycophytes come from? — A piece of the story from the Silurian of peri-Gondwana. *Gondwana Res.* **45**, 180–190. (doi: 10.1016/j.gr.2017.02.001)
70. Lang WH, Cookson IC. 1935 On a flora, including vascular land plants, associated with *Monograptus*, in rocks of Silurian age, from Victoria, Australia. *Philos. Trans. R Soc. Lond. B* **224**, 421–449. (doi: 10.1098/rstb.1935.0004)
71. Edwards D, Geng BY, Li CS. 2016 New Plants from the Lower Devonian Pingyipu Group, Jiangyou County, Sichuan Province, China. *PLoS ONE* **11**, e0163549. (doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0163549)
72. Matsunaga KKS, Tomescu AMF. 2017 An organismal concept for *Sengelia radicans* gen. et sp. nov. — Morphology and natural history of an Early Devonian lycophyte. *Ann. Bot.* **119**, 1097–1113. (doi: 10.1093/aob/mcw277)
73. Li CS, Edwards D. 1992 A new genus of early land plants with novel strobilar construction from the Lower Devonian Posongchong Formation, Yunnan Province, China. *Palaeontology* **35**, 257–272.
74. Zhu X, Xue JZ, Hao SG, Wang DM. 2011 A new species of *Adoketophyton* from the Lower Devonian (Pragian) Posongchong Formation of Yunnan, China. *Rev. Palaeobot. Palynol.* **164**, 238–246. (doi: 10.1016/j.revpalbo.2011.01.003)
75. Kerp H, Wellman CH, Krings M, Kearney P, Hass H. 2013 Reproductive organs and in situ spores of *Asteroxylon mackiei* Kidston & Lang, the most complex plant from the Lower Devonian Rhynie Chert. *Int. J. Plant Sci.* **173**, 293–308. (doi: 10.1086/668613)
76. Hao SG. 1989 *Gumuia zyzata*—A new plant from the Lower Devonian of Yunnan, China. *Acta Bot. Sin.* **31**, 954–961.
77. Geng BY. 1985 *Huia recurvata*—A new plant from Lower Devonian of Southeastern Yunnan, China. *Acta Bot. Sin.* **27**, 419–426.
78. Hueber FM. 1971 *Sawdonia ornata*: a new name for *Psilophyton princeps* var. *ornatum*. *Taxon* **20**, 641–642. (doi: 10.2307/1218284)

79. Li CS, Edwards D. 1995 A re-investigation of Halle's *Drepanophycus spinaeformis* Göpp. From the Lower Devonian of Yunnan Province, southern China. *Bot. J. Linn. Soc.* **118**, 163–192. (doi: 10.1111/j.1095-8339.1995.tb00468.x)
80. Wang DM, Hao SG, Wang Q. 2003 *Hsüa deflexa* sp. nov. from the Xujiachong Formation (Lower Devonian) of eastern Yunnan, China. *Bot. J. Linn. Soc.* **142**, 255–271. (doi: 10.1046/j.1095-8339.2003.00187.x)
81. Li CS. 1982 *Hsüa robusta*, a new land plant from the Lower Devonian of Yunnan, China. *Acta Phytotaxon. Sin.* **20**, 331–342.
82. Wang DM, Hao SG. 2001 A new species of vascular plants from the Xujiachong Formation (Lower Devonian) of Yunnan Province, China. *Rev. Palaeobot. Palynol.* **114**, 157–174. (doi: 10.1016/s0034-6667(01)00041-0)
83. Geng BY, Zhu WQ. 1994 New observations on *Drepanophycus spinaeformis* from the Lower Devonian of Guizhou, China. *Acta Phytotaxon. Sin.* **32**, 345–348.
84. Hueber FM. 1983 A new species of *Baragwanathia* from the Sextant Formation (Emsian) Northern Ontario, Canada. *Bot. J. Linn. Soc.* **86**, 57–79. (doi: 10.1111/j.1095-8339.1983.tb00717.x)
85. Li CS, Hueber FM, Hotton CL. 2000 A neotype for *Drepanophycus spinaeformis* Göppert 1852. *Can. J. Bot.* **78**, 889–902. (doi: 10.1139/b00-062)
86. Gensel PG, Andrews HN, Forbes WH. 1975 A new species of *Sawdonia* with notes on the origin of microphylls and lateral sporangia. *Bot. Gaz.* **136**, 50–62. (doi: 10.1086/336782)
87. Berry CM, Gensel PG. 2019 Late Mid Devonian *Sawdonia* (Zosterophyllopsida) from Venezuela. *Int. J. Plant Sci.* **180**, 540–557. (doi: 10.1086/702940)